

Evaluation of Flow Rate of Three Different Endodontic Root Canal Sealers: An In Vitro Study

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Abstract

Aim: To evaluate and compare the flow rate of three different root canal sealers.

Materials and Methods: Three different types of root canal sealers such as Rootfyx, Epoxyseal and Zical were taken to evaluate the flow rate. The sealers were mixed dropped on the center of glass slab. Three minutes later, another glass plate was placed centrally above the sealer, followed by weight to determine the flow. After 10 minutes from mixing, the weight was removed and diameter of the sealer was measured. Five determinations were carried out and the mean value was calculated to the nearest scale.

Results: The mean diameters of the average flow rate of the sealers Rootfyx, Epoxyseal and Zical were 25.12mm, 23.62mm and 21.08mm respectively.

Conclusion: All the three sealers had the minimum criteria for the flow according to ISO specification. Rootfyx, bioceramic based sealer showed greater flow rate and Zical showed lower flow rate.

Keywords: Rootfyx, Epoxyseal, Zical, flow rate, root canal sealer

Introduction

Dentists utilise endodontic root canal sealers to fill and seal the space inside the tooth's root canal system during root canal treatments. Root canal sealer's main objective is to stop fluids and bacteria from entering the canal system, which could cause the tooth to become infected again. Zinc oxide-eugenol, calcium hydroxide, glass ionomer, resin-based, silicone-based, or bioceramic materials are some of the components commonly found in endodontic sealers. Every kind of sealer has unique qualities and benefits. A root canal sealer's main function is to fill in the gaps and defects in the root canal system so that a fluid-tight seal is formed. By doing this, the danger of reinfection is decreased since microorganisms and their metabolites are kept out of the canal. Endodontic sealants ought to be bio compatible, which means the surrounding tissues shouldn't experience any negative reactions or toxicity from them. For root canal therapy to be successful over the long run, bio compatibility is essential. The comfort of handling

throughout the procedure might be impacted by the different setting times of sealers. While certain sealers set faster than others, the dentist has more working time with the latter. Some sealers are made to stick to the gutta-percha, the core material used to fill the canal space, as well as the sides of the canal. This improves the root canal filling's stability and closure. Endodontic sealants ought to be visible on dental radiographs, or radiopaque. This makes it possible for dentists to precisely evaluate the root canal filling's quality and placement both during and after the surgery. In order to preserve their integrity and sealing power over time, root canal sealers should ideally be able to withstand resorption. Thus, bacterial leakage into the canal is prevented. The effectiveness of root canal therapy depends on

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the durability of endodontic sealants. Sealers should minimise the chance of reinfection and maintain the health of the tooth by creating a strong seal that holds for many years.¹

According to Schilder, three dimensional seal of the root canal is provided by root canal sealer. The term "flow" describes the endodontic sealer's capacity to efficiently enter and occupy the complex crevices found within the root canal system. To ensure a thorough and uniform seal, a sealer with good flow qualities can enter dentinal tubules, accessory canals, and imperfections. There are two viscosities of endodontic sealers: low and high. Low viscosity sealers flow more easily and can fit into narrower spaces in the root canal system. High viscosity sealers, on the other hand, might be chosen because of their capacity to withstand excessive flow and hold their position during root canal obturation. Thixotropic behaviour refers to the tendency of several endodontic sealers to increase viscosity at rest and reduce it under shear stress. This characteristic improves the sealer's capacity to seal by allowing it to flow freely during application but preventing it from escaping the canal once it is in place. Overall, the flow properties of an endodontic sealer play a significant role in its ability to effectively seal the root canal system and contribute to the success of root canal treatment. According to ISO specification sealer should have diameter of more than 20mm. This study evaluated the flow rate of three different sealers i.e. bioceramic based- Rootfyx, epoxy based- EpoxySeal and resin based- Zical.

Materials And Methods

The endodontic sealers that were used in the study were Root fyx, Epoxyseal and Zical. These sealers were measured according to the standards of the International Organisation for Standardisation specification. The sealers were mixed with spatula until obtaining a homogenous mixture. A volume of 0.05ml from 1-ml syringe was dropped on the center of glass slab (100x 150mm). Three minutes later, another glass plate was placed centrally above the sealer. It was followed by weight of mass 100g to make total mass on the plate $120 \pm 2g$ to determine the flow. After 10 minutes the weight was removed and the values of maximum and minimum diameters are measured with vernier calliper. If the mean of the two diameters agree to within 1mm and the samples were uniformly circular, then it is taken as flow of the sample. If not, the test was repeated. Five determinations were carried out and the mean value was calculated to the nearest scale.

Results

The ISO specification requires that the diameter of the sealer should not be less than 20 mm. All the three sealers Rootfyx, Epoxyseal and Zical conformed to the ISO specification. All the three sealers met the minimum required criteria of more than 20 mm in diameter. The average of the mean diameters of the sealers Rootfyx, Epoxyseal and Zical were 25.12mm, 23.62mm and 21.08mm respectively.

Discussion

Research has been done on a number of root canal sealer characteristics, including bio compatibility, anti bacterial activity, film thickness, disintegration, dissolving, and setting time. A root canal sealer's ability to pass through spaces between the master and accessory cones, accessory canals, and dentin's tiny abnormalities is also crucial. When flow and working time are drastically reduced, it becomes difficult to work with a material effectively, which raises the possibility of a void developing.²

One of the crucial stages of endodontic treatment is root canal filling, which tries to fully fill the root canal system using filling materials with sufficient biological as well as physicochemical attributes. The flow of root canal sealers is one of its key characteristics when it comes to root canal obturation. For any endodontic sealer to reach and seal the apical foramen and lateral dentinal wall abnormalities, there must be a satisfactory flow during the working time.³

Studies have been conducted on a number of root canal sealer characteristics, including antibacterial activity, bio compatibility, film thickness, dis integration, solubility, and setting time.⁴ Additionally, a root canal sealer's flow must be appropriate to penetrate spaces between the master and accessory cones, dentin's narrow abnormalities, and accessory canals. Reduced flow and working time make it harder to deal with a material efficiently, which raises the possibility of a void developing.⁵ A number of variables could affect how well endodontic sealants penetrate small spaces in the root canal system. Several factors appear to be crucial in facilitating sealer penetration, including the obturation technique employed, the contact area, the dimension of irregularities, accessibility to the complexity, and the flow rate of the sealer. Composition of the sealers also play a major role in their flow rate.⁶

According to Dash A K, MTA fillapex showed greater flow rate compared to other sealers.⁷ According to Bernardes, AH plus showed greater flow rate com-

The flow test of this test was conducted according to ISO standards and all the three-sealer showed more than the minimum criteria, that is above 20mm. Rootfyx sealer showed greater flow which then followed by Epoxyseal and the least was showed by Zical. The better flow of rootfyx compared to others can be due to its composition calcium silicate and tantalum oxide. Zical showed comparatively low flow rate. It can be due to the contents. Rootfyx is a bioceramic based sealer whereas Epoxyseal and Zical are eugenol based.

Further research is required to evaluate the performance of these sealers and their role in endodontic therapy.

Conclusion

Within limitations of this study all the three sealers had the minimum criteria for the flow according to ISO specification. Rootfyx sealer has greater flow rate and Zical had lower flow rate.

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